

BEHAVIORAL ANALYSIS OF ROCKY INTERTIDAL AGGREGATING ANEMONE IN RESPONSE
TO HUMAN AND NON-HUMAN DEBRIS

by

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ORCID ID: 0009-0008-2763-064X

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11479454

A Project Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements to Graduate with University Honors

The University Honors Program
California State University, Fullerton

May 2024

Approved by:

Date:

5/17/2024

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5/24/2024

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Abstract:

Human pollution has had a tremendous impact on rocky intertidal life. This project addresses the questions: What proportion of aggregating anemones have human-left debris attached to their body columns, and what behaviors influence this? Do anemones preferentially pick up natural debris or human debris, even if both are available? It emphasizes their interactions with human pollution factors, further highlighting the impact of pollution on rocky intertidal life. I propose to count and determine the proportion of anemone with human-left and natural debris in the field. Additionally, I will pay particular attention to designated areas with high anemone counts. This will help to recognize the anemone distribution across the rocky intertidal zone to consider if it plays a role in the type of debris on their body columns. This study will utilize observational and experimental methods and technologies to expand our understanding of the detrimental effect of human activity on aggregating anemones – an essential California species. I aim to advance further knowledge of the biology and behavior of aggregating anemones. (169)

Introduction:

The aggregating anemone, *Anthopleura elegantissima*, is an invertebrate species often found in the west coast of North America (Bingham et. al, 2011). Their distribution across their habitat includes zones that experience both high tide and low tide (Bingham et. al, 2011). They typically develop high population sizes despite the abundance of many other rocky intertidal organisms (Bingham et. al, 2011). The *Anthopleura elegantissima* are able to withstand drastic fluctuations in temperature and their external environment, allowing them to persist both under and over the water's surface as the tide shifts (Bingham et. al, 2011). The varying temperatures impact whether or not they fully close or open their tentacles to the surrounding air or water (Barrera, 2021). The anemones typically keep their tentacles closed upon air exposure and reopen themselves when submerged in water (Dyken and Shick, 1984). Aggregating anemones are species that thrive in Southern California rocky intertidal zone environments using their morphological components to adapt to changes in the environment and coexist with other species around them.

Aggregating anemones are sedentary organisms belonging to the phylum Cnidaria (Shick, 1991). A phylum is a taxonomic category used to rank organisms, and *Anthopleura elegantissima* share the same phylum as many marine organisms, such as jellyfish and corals (Shick, 1991). They have a tube-shaped body column that is typically twice as long as it is wide, along with an oral disk at the top surrounded by tentacles (Shick, 1991). On their tentacles normally reside microalgae called zooxanthellae that provide a carbon source to the anemones, which the anemones use for energy (Shick, 1991). These algae have a symbiotic relationship with the anemone, particularly a mutualistic relationship; this means that the two organisms help

each other survive and mutually benefit one another (Shick, 1991). The anemone bends towards the sunlight to grant the microalgae the sunlight it needs to photosynthesize, and the anemone then uses the carbon produced from the microalgae, demonstrating a give-and-take relationship between the two organisms (Shick, 1991). Aggregating anemones are carnivores that feed on various organisms in the intertidal zone, such as small fish and plankton, and their tentacles have structures called nematocysts that help them to feed by stinging and paralyzing their prey (Shick, 1991).

The symbiotic relationship that aggregating anemones have, alongside the fluctuations in temperature in the rocky intertidal environment, indicates that temperature plays a key role in the behavior of this species. For instance, one study found that temporal changes influence anemones' tendency to aggregate, or group together. In the warmer months of the year, aggregations of *Anthopleura elegantissima* were more prevalent in the anemones' distribution across the rocky intertidal zone, suggesting aggregation as a possible behavioral response to avoid desiccation as temperatures increase (Bingham et. al, 2011). This behavioral implication is key to understanding how anemones are distributed across the rocky intertidal zone, a primary point in this study. Aggregating anemone distribution can provide information on their response to external factors. The temporal behavior of aggregating anemones can potentially provide insight into similar behaviors influenced by other conditional elements of the rocky intertidal zone, such as the materials available for the aggregating anemones to attach onto themselves.

Aggregating anemones are known to attach debris onto their body columns (Shick, 1991). The main hypothesis regarding the function of this behavior is that it regulates body temperature during the transitions between low and high tides (Dyken and Shick, 1984). The small debris attached onto their bodies are hypothesized to regulate body temperature by preventing

desiccation in conditions of high sunlight, as well as to reflect light off of the body columns of the anemones (Dyken and Shick, 1984). Usually, the debris observed on their body columns consist of small shell or rock pieces scattered throughout the outside of their body, and are particularly light in color, highlighting their potential to reflect light (Shick, 1991). However, as the human population has increased and beaches have become tourist destinations more accessible to the general public as social settings, the amount of human-left pollution on these beaches and rocky intertidal zones has also increased. As such, various organisms are affected, primarily in negative ways. (Beaumont et. al, 2019).

Previous studies and observations on anemone species have shown that anemones attach debris onto their body columns. The debris are hypothesized to act as protection from the sun when the tide is low (Dyken and Shick, 1984). This is because aggregating anemones contain photosynthetic symbionts that harbor chlorophyll (Dyken and Shick, 1984). When anemones with debris on their body columns are exposed to prolonged sunlight during a low tide, they retain much more chlorophyll than anemones without debris exposed to sunlight during low tide conditions, suggesting that the debris act as a sunscreen to both prevent desiccation and retain chlorophyll to upkeep the symbiont relationship (Dyken and Shick, 1984). When anemones are subject to thermal injuries, however, they appear to form a zone of repair relatively quickly, normally within 48-72 hours of thermal injury (Patterson and Landolt, 1978). This zone of repair protects the anemones from secondary infection and begins tissue repair processes, and this process appears across multiple species of cnidaria (Patterson and Landolt, 1978). This suggests that aggregating anemones have efficient protection and repair systems that prevent thermal injury and allow for fast tissue and cellular regeneration of damages on their body columns. These facts are important to consider in low and high tide and their tendency to attach debris

onto their body columns because it appears as though the debris serve a purpose to the anemones' survival in their habitat. The sun protection hypothesis from Dykens and Shick can provide a possible explanation into this behavioral pattern because the thermal protection systems present in aggregating anemones' biology, as well as their distribution methods in warmer temperatures, suggest a relationship between temperature and anemone covering behavior. The concepts of debris attachment and temporal behavior in aggregating anemones are prime inspirations behind this project, with the aim to better understand these organisms and the behaviors they implement to adapt to their changing environment. However, this study has a goal to expand upon these ideas by exploring them in the context of human pollution and determining how pollution possibly changes these behaviors.

Human pollution factors are a growing concern to not only humans, but to plants, animals, and even entire ecosystems. Plastic debris in particular have become extremely common in Southern California, and are often broken down into small microplastics scattered throughout marine areas, including the rocky intertidal zone (Beck, 2022). Studies on plastic pollution in marine ecosystems is a large area of study that encompasses many different issues, with one primary area of study focusing on how the organisms in these environments are affected directly. Plastic pollution continues to grow alongside almost all forms of pollution, and the increase in human residency near marine ecosystems has exposed rocky intertidal zones to high numbers of plastic trash pollution (Beck, 2022). A common concern is whether this plastic pollution can disrupt the balance of the ecosystems by potentially altering symbiotic relationships, such as that of aggregating anemones and their microalgae symbionts (Beck, 2022). Studies of this caliber would need to take place over long periods of time to decipher true relationships between plastic pollution and symbiotic relationships (Beck, 2022). Various studies suggest that the presence of

food or chemical cues of prey present on human-left debris, particularly plastic waste, increases the likelihood of anemone species taking in the debris. After obtaining the potential nutritional value present on the human-left debris, they ingest the debris (Romano de Orte et. al, 2019).

Typically, human-left debris is deemed as harmful to aquatic life, but studies suggest that there can be a benefit to the anemones attaching these debris onto their body columns.

This study aims to address questions inspired by previous studies and research to delve deeper into the potential impact of human-left debris on aggregating anemones, particularly if anemones with human-left debris are actually present in the field and whether or not these debris might pose benefits or harm to the anemones. Additionally, this project is inspired by the work of a previous graduate student in the Burnaford Lab, Trina Miller, who tracked trash across different rocky intertidal zones, and who directly saw aggregating anemones with certain trash debris like plastic attached onto their body columns during her studies out at various Southern California rocky intertidal sites (Miller and Burnaford, 2022). The questions addressed in study are: 1) What proportion of aggregating anemones use human debris for cover? 2) How does the introduction of human-left debris influence their behavior to cover their body column? 3) How might debris be beneficial to the anemones? How might debris be harmful?

The study utilizes observational methods and highlights future experimental methods to help understand how human pollution affects aggregating anemones in their behaviors and survival strategies in response to changing environments and growing plastic pollution.

Aggregating anemones are an important rocky intertidal California species, and this study can build upon and expand the current understanding of the effect of human activity on them.

Methodology:

This study focused on assessing the behavioral and biological implications of aggregating anemones and the debris, both natural and human-left, they attach onto their body columns to gain insight into why they do this. It utilized observational methods, and will later expand to use experimental methods and technologies, in an attempt to answer the questions this study aims to address. The project entails two types of data collection: one in the field and one in the lab.

The field observations took place at the Point Fermin rocky intertidal zone in San Pedro, Los Angeles County, California. The aim was to quantify anemone abundance and categorize debris present on their body columns. Transects were laid across designated areas with high anemone counts to understand their distribution across the rocky intertidal zone. The data collected was then quantified into bar graphs to analyze and further assess whether their distribution across the rocky intertidal zone plays a role into the type of debris on their body columns. The total sample size counted was 518 aggregating anemones. To collect the data, two 25 m long transects were laid out, with one facing left and the other facing right from the center of the site, a designated site containing high anemone counts and trash pollution (Miller and Burnaford, 2022).

Figure 1. Site area at Point Fermin, San Pedro, CA. Pipe is visible by coordinates

At each one meter point on the transect, a random coin toss was performed to designate whether the anemones would be counted on the right or left side of the transect line, with heads designated as right of the transect and tails designated as left of the transect. The total number of aggregating anemones were counted at each 1 m point, recording whether or not they were found on the rocky intertidal surface or submerged in the tide pools. The number of aggregating anemones with human-left debris were noted. Then, the different types of debris were categorized on the anemone: human-left debris, natural debris, and no debris, all to obtain a proportion of the different debris types. The human-left debris were further classified into precisely what types were found. The goal of the field aspect of this study is to answer the question: what proportion of anemones in the field have human-left debris attached onto their body columns?

Figure 2. Observational study done at Point Fermin, San Pedro, CA. Transect line is 25 m long.

The second part of the study entails a pending lab experiment. A small number of aggregating anemones, 40 total, will be collected in a cooler with a waterproof temperature data logger and transported to the tank room lab at California State University, Fullerton, where they will be maintained in a 60-gallon recirculating seawater tank at ambient water temperature and

fed one shrimp pellet per day to maintain their health and keep them in optimal conditions for the experimental study. In the next portion of the study, the anemones will be removed from the tanks, and then metal forceps will be used to remove and examine various debris from the anemones' body columns. The classification of the type of material for each debris will be recorded and categorized as either human-left or natural. Additionally, the anemones will be observed for any visible injury upon debris removal to understand the effects of the debris on their body columns. The goal of this laboratory experiment is to examine the purpose and effects of the debris on the physiology of individual anemones and observe if the debris can potentially be harmful to the anemones or not.

Lastly, as a second part of the laboratory experiment, anemones will be randomly assigned to either a 'light' or 'dark' treatment. Animals in the dark treatment will be maintained without light for two days and will be placed in a separate tank than animals in the light treatment. Then, the anemones will be presented with a variety of options of prepared materials, primarily plastic, to assess their preferences for human debris versus natural debris as cover. Furthermore, this portion of the study will test whether they prefer a certain type of human debris over another by observing patterns in the debris contents on the anemones' body columns. The prepared plastic materials and natural debris will roughly all be the same size to best reflect the debris observed in the field studies. After the two days, the experiment will end, and the amount of debris attached to each anemone will be quantified. Additionally, the debris will be categorized into natural and non-natural, or human-left, debris, similar to how they were in the field observational study. For the light treatment, animals will be placed in tanks with exposure to natural levels of sunlight. All other conditions will be the same for the animals in the two treatment groups. The goal of the treatment group study is to test the sun protection hypothesis

presented by Dykens and Shick to test how effective certain debris materials are at protecting the anemones' body columns and physiology from exposure to prolonged sunlight based on the distribution of debris found on the body columns after the treatments.

Results

The observational study took place over two different days out at Point Fermin in San Pedro, CA. This specific site was chosen based on previous work done by Trina Miller, where she found various forms of trash distributed throughout the site and observed instances of aggregating anemones holding onto the trash (Trina and Burnaford, 2022). The aimed sample size for this study was around 500 aggregating anemones, with a total of 518 counted after the study. Upon quantification, the anemones were categorized by their debris types: natural only, natural and trash, or no cover. The predicted results were that the majority of the anemones would only have natural debris, a much smaller proportion would have some trash cover, and a very small amount would have no cover whatsoever. The obtained results from the observational study are illustrated in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3. Proportion of aggregating anemones based on cover type. N = 518 anemones.

According to Figure 3, the majority of the anemones out of the sample size of 518 total were observed with only natural cover, and the exact number observed was 467. It is important to note that, aside from those with no cover, all aggregating anemones were found with natural debris as cover. Those that also were found with some trash cover were counted to 49 anemones, and only two anemones were found with no cover whatsoever.

After the anemones were counted and were categorized as shown in Figure 3, further classification was done on the types of trash observed in the 49 anemones found with trash cover to determine if the anemones had a preference for a certain type of pollutant debris or if one type of pollutant debris was more abundant than the other. The results for this are shown in Figure 4 below.

Figure 4. Cover material types on anemones with human-left debris in the rocky intertidal zone. All anemones had some natural material; no anemones were found with only human-left debris. N = 49 anemones with trash cover.

This figure illustrates the different types of trash found on the anemones observed with trash cover. According to the figure, the only two trash cover types observed were plastic and glass. Out of these, there were more anemones observed with plastic debris attached onto their body columns as opposed to glass debris. Out of the 49 anemones with trash cover, 38 were

observed with plastic debris and 11 were found with glass debris. Examples of an aggregating anemone with plastic debris and one with glass debris are shown in the images below.

Figure 5. Aggregating anemones at Point Fermin, San Pedro, CA, with human-left debris attached onto their body columns. Left picture: glass debris. Right picture: plastic debris.

It is important to highlight that these anemones pictured are also present with natural debris on their body columns. During this observational study, no anemones were found with only human-left debris on their bodies, and those found with human-left debris typically only contained one piece of trash, with the rest of the cover being natural materials.

For the laboratory portion of this study, the distribution of the types of debris presented to the aggregating anemones, namely pieces of plastic and pieces of shells and rocks, will be studied in both the light and dark treatments over a period of 48 hours upon exposure to both human debris and natural debris in the experimental conditions. This data will be used to further understand the sun protection hypothesis and determine whether the type of debris is significant in protecting aggregating anemones against desiccation during prolonged sun exposure. Particularly, the number of anemones will be counted across both treatment groups and will be categorized into three categories: Natural debris only, natural and trash debris, and trash debris only. The sample size for this experiment is approximately 40 aggregating anemones. A figure highlighting the predicted results for this experiment is shown below.

Figure 6. Predicted results for cover material types on anemones in light and dark treatment groups. N = 40 anemones total.

This figure illustrates potential results based on previous research surrounding anemone covering behavior, as well as recorded observations of anemones in the field. It is predicted that the light treatment will yield aggregating anemones with a majority of natural debris, and that those in the dark treatment will have more trash debris, as highlighted in the leftmost and rightmost columns of the figure, respectively.

Discussion

According to the results obtained from the observational study, there are instances of aggregating anemones with human-left debris on their body. Although the overall proportion is relatively small, with only 49 out of 518 anemones surveyed containing human-left debris as shown in Figure 3, these observations provide insight into the behavior of aggregating sea anemones. The prevalence of trash on the rocky intertidal zone appears to have an influence in the behavior of aggregating anemones because a small proportion of them use these pollutant debris as cover alongside the natural cover typical of the species. Figure 5 illustrates this well, with the

aggregating anemones containing primarily natural debris but having one or two pieces of human-left debris.

The observational study illustrated the distribution of aggregating anemones in the rocky intertidal zone. All aggregating anemones found above the pools had their tentacles closed, and the vast majority in the pools had their tentacles open. These field observations were conducted during low tide, but there were still some anemones observed in the pools during the data collection. This observation has implications for the sun protection hypothesis presented by Dykens and Shick (1984). Almost all of the anemone from the observations were reported to have cover, as indicated by Figure 3, where only two out of the 518 anemones were found without any cover at all, suggesting that the debris act as a sunscreen to protect the aggregating anemones during low tide conditions the consequent changes in temperature. This provides a key insight into the behavior of these organisms, highlighting how they incorporate the attachment of debris as a survival strategy to help them persist during temporal and environmental changes. Further testing of this sun protection hypothesis will be performed in the pending laboratory experimental portion of this study to determine the effectiveness of trash debris as cover in conditions of exposed sunlight.

Another component of the sun protection hypothesis this study aims to further expand on is whether or not the type of trash plays a role in the effectiveness of debris as sun protection. In the field observations, only two types of trash debris were found: plastic and glass. As quantified in Figure 4, there were more anemones observed with plastic debris compared to glass debris, with 38 having plastic and 11 having glass debris. This can possibly suggest that the anemones have a preference for plastic debris over glass debris, which can be due to the potential presence of nutrients on microplastics, as examined in the study by Romano de Orte (2019). While this

possibility will not be tested during the experimental portion of the study, it could provide a possible explanation for the anemones attaching onto plastic debris. What can be tested however, is whether or not plastic debris might be more beneficial in terms of sun protection. When comparing glass and plastic as materials themselves, glass typically allows light to penetrate through it easier than plastic does, especially clear glasses versus colored plastics, which were observed in the field. This could indicate that plastics, particularly light-colored plastics, could serve as more effective debris against sunlight conditions, since they would more-closely resemble the natural white debris of shell or rock that can reflect sunlight off of the anemones' body columns. However, further testing and studies would need to be conducted in the laboratory to come to a concise conclusion about this and determine if there really is a difference between glass and plastic debris in their effectiveness to protect the anemone against sunlight. To conclude off of the current observations in the field, the anemones appear to have a preference for plastics. In Figure 5, the anemone on the right has two pieces of plastic on it, and was the only anemone found with more than one piece of human-left debris on it. In the laboratory experiments, anemone will be presented with multiple pieces of experimental human-left debris, primarily plastic, to test how much they would attach onto their body columns, which will then be further analyzed for sunscreen effectiveness in the light and dark treatment groups.

Figure 6 presents predicted data for the light and dark treatment experiment. Approximately 40 anemones will be exposed to different debris types, both natural and human-left, and will be tested for which debris they hold onto during the 48-hour experimental period. The predictions for this is that, in the light treatment, the anemones will have a greater preference for natural debris. This is based off of the observational study performed, particularly the data performed in Figure 3. The light treatment will more closely mimic the real-life

conditions out in the rocky intertidal field when the observational study was conducted, because it was during low tide and during a period of prolonged sunlight exposure. If the majority of anemones observed then had natural debris, then it is predicted that the anemones in the light treatment will exhibit the same behavior and primarily attach natural debris onto themselves. This is because the sun protection hypothesis argues that the reason aggregating anemones attach debris onto their body columns is to redirect sunlight, protecting them from desiccation and physiological harm. If most anemones attach natural debris onto themselves in the field, this suggests that natural debris are better-suited for protection against sunlight than human-left debris. Thus, it is predicted that anemones in the dark treatment will not have as strong of a preference for natural debris, and so more anemones with human-left debris will be observed after the 48-hour period. However, Figure 6 simply represents the predicted data based on previous research and on the observational study conducted in the field. Until the experiment is performed, no tangible evidence can indicate whether or not human-left debris are less efficient at acting as a sunscreen than natural debris, nor if anemones in the dark treatment will have more human-left debris than natural debris for this reason.

All of these findings, and the previous research they align with, indicate that aggregating anemones are an adaptable species. It is already known that they are able to withstand drastic changes in temperature in their outside environment, as well as find ways to protect themselves from desiccation whilst thriving in non-ideal conditions during low tide and prolonged sunlight. Unlike many other marine organisms, aggregating anemones seem to have a unique response to human pollutants, which appear to pose no harm or threat when presented in small amounts. In fact, previous research, combined with further laboratory experiments as a part of this study, may

even suggest that these human-left debris can be beneficial to anemones in the same way that natural-left debris are.

These observations support the presence of aggregating anemones with human-left debris in the rocky intertidal zone. With this information, there are some next steps that can be taken to solidify these findings and further investigate the relationships between human-left debris and anemone behavior and survival. More observational studies can be conducted in the field to determine more proportions of anemones with human-left debris compared to those with only natural debris. These can be conducted at different sites all throughout Southern California. Additionally, choosing the area within each site could potentially be significant; for example, areas close to human activity could potentially have more human pollutants in the rocky intertidal zone compared to the more secluded areas, resulting in a higher proportion of anemones with human-left debris attached onto their body columns. This highlights that the area of study is important when performing these experiments. More data can also be collected on anemones that specifically highlights the differences in the tide, or those above the water's surface versus below the water's surface, to see if there is any significant data supporting the hypothesis that aggregating anemones exposed to more sunlight have more debris on them to prevent desiccation and physiological harm. Furthermore, studies can be done on the effectiveness of debris types against prolonged sun exposure to determine which would be the best to protect the anemones' body columns. For anemones that are harmed during these processes, studies can be conducted on their regeneration time, specifically highlighting how they heal and the behavior they acquire during the healing process in terms of debris attachment. Previous studies suggest that the attachment of debris poses no harm to aggregating anemones, but it is still unsure whether this is true for human-left debris. The prevalence of thriving

anemones with human-left debris in their natural habitat could propose that the presence of human-left debris does not harm the anemones and instead acts similarly to other debris.

However, there may also be a potential threshold that can determine how many human-left debris on an anemone are harmless versus when the amount can cause potential harm. Additionally, potential studies that delve into the presence of food on human-left debris pieces could serve as an explanation for why aggregating anemones take these pieces of debris in and onto their body columns, further exploring their feeding habits. Consequently, even if aggregating anemones appear unbothered by the presence of human-left debris, there could be implications for these anemones harming other organisms that predate on aggregating anemones if those organisms ingest the human-left debris. Overall, the observation of aggregating anemones with human-left debris on their body columns opens the door for many potential studies to test why the anemones might behave this way, what benefits or harms the debris can cause them, and how this phenomenon can affect the overall ecosystem of Southern California rocky intertidal zones.

To conclude, the results of this study demonstrate that there is a proportion of aggregating anemones that hold onto human-left debris, but that this proportion is relatively small compared to the proportion of anemones that hold onto natural-left debris like rocks and shell pieces. Additionally, the most commonly-found human-left debris on the body columns of aggregating anemones was small pieces of plastic. These findings highlight the behavior of aggregating anemones as an adaptable species that can withstand changes in their environment, from the temporal changes, changes in the tide, changes in sunlight exposure, to even changes in the types of materials present for them to attach onto themselves for protection and survival. Human pollution has been a growing problem for decades, and the effects are prevalent in beaches all throughout Southern California. Aggregating anemones are an important Southern California

rocky intertidal species, and studying these organisms can provide a greater understanding into the impact that humans leave on rocky intertidal ecosystems, allowing for more education and awareness of the effects of human pollution.

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